

Collaborative governance literature study in the development of tourist villages in Indonesia

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Abstract

Collaborative governance becomes essential in the process of achieving common goals. The role of collaboration needs to be encouraged with the same goals and interests that every actor can accommodate with an interest in building a tourism village. The development of tourist villages will occur with capital in the form of tourism potential and actors with various competencies. This research is a qualitative study with a literature study approach. The collaboration that is carried out stems from the need and awareness of the process of developing a tourist village that needs to be carried out together. Leadership is required to create a platform that will be used to encourage collaborative processes. Tourism village development can be developed by combining various competencies from different actors. Actors who will collaborate in developing tourist villages need to be aware of a common goal more significant than the interests they carry. The government can encourage collaboration forums to create certain institutions or platforms regularly to reinforce short-term goals.

Keywords: *collaborative governance; village tourism; actor; interest*

A. Introduction

The village development process cannot be carried out alone by the village government and needs to collaborate with other parties following the principles developed in the village law. The pattern of management using collaborative governance can be used as a method of implementing development by the village government. Collaborative governance (Bevir, 2007) is how the government involves the community, social organizations, the private sector, and other stakeholders in every policy process. This process provides opportunities for various parties to contribute according to their abilities and needs with the platform that has been delivered (Ansell & Gash, 2018).

The concept of collaborative governance is also a place to see interest groups on specific issues. The form of collaboration will also follow from the subject being front, and there is no standard form in the collaborative governance process. The benefits that can be obtained from the concept of collaborative governance (Bevir, 2007) are increasing discourse from various points of view, finding policies that are more flexible on these issues, and strengthening the legitimacy of these policies because more interest groups support them. In addition, the participation of stakeholders will be more diverse (Newman et al., 2004).

Village businesses in carrying out development also need to be strengthened with assistance from other parties who have other affairs but with the same goal of developing the

village. Arumsari et al., (2017) encourage village governments to consciously partner with other parties to achieve village development. The tourism village, which is currently becoming a village development trend, is a development process that must be carried out correctly and conceptually. The village government cannot hope for optimism in visiting people for some issues, but it also needs planning and support (Amil et al., 2019). Planning needs to be done carefully and purposefully, and consider the business opportunities of each actor involved in the collaboration process (Razzak & Qodir, 2020). So it is necessary to have a study linking the village government's efforts to become a tourist village and a collaborative governance approach to achieve this goal.

B. Methods

The research was conducted using a qualitative approach which aims to analyze in depth the relationship between collaborative governance and the development of tourist villages. This method also considers the adequacy of the data to be used and processed to find and strengthen these relationships.

C. Results and Discussion

Leadership

Leadership in the collaboration process is essential to encourage initiators and maintain the continuity of the collaboration itself. Collaborative governance requires initiative from one of the parties to attract and bring up collaborative activities (Page, 2010). Efforts to bring about this collaboration must direct each actor to pursue and fight for the big goal. The village government, the most interested party in village development, must strengthen its development goals and show them to every actor invited to collaborate. Issues in the leadership aspect are opportunities for internal conflict and for the collaboration process to break down (Zachrisson et al., 2021). This issue concerns the demands of various actors to create a tourist village according to their expectations (Debnath & Bardhan, 2018).

The village head is the actor most expected to lead the collaboration process. The ability of the village head to delegate his duties and authority an emphasis on organizational needs (De Rosa et al., 2019). Another strength is the ability to see problems and approach solutions that must be carried out and held by the village head. Another demand on the leadership of the village head is to arrange for each actor to maintain their hopes in the collaboration process even though their interests have been achieved (Untari, 2019).

Actors

The actors involved in village development are numerous and varied according to their potential roles and potential activities. Institutions that exist in the village and can become actors in tourism-based village development, such as farmer groups related to agricultural potential, youth associations, and BUMDes related to the village economy, will grow PADes. In developing a tourist village, each actor has a function, business, and resources (Rohimah et al., 2018).

The Penta helix approach analyzes the roles and functions of each actor according to their potential (Febriyani & Aliya, 2020). The community supports the village government's role in making policies to comply with and monitor the policies made. The local and central governments' roles must coordinate to regulate and support development data. Academics have a role to play with new knowledge resources and access to technology. The private sector governs the flow of capital and strengthens the community's economic system. The mass media has a role in distributing information to various parties, and the community is the party that becomes the object. It will be encouraged to become the subject of village development.

Strengthening interests and relations between actors is vital because each actor has different interests. In developing a tourist village, the village government must be a party that has a role in orchestrating other actors according to their authority and function. The village government can carry out village autonomy granted by the central government with assistance from the provincial and district governments.

Aligning goals and strengthening interests

Interests are always inherent in each party and become a driving force in their activities. The development of a tourist village needs to be realized so that every actor has interests and hopes for the success of developing a tourist village (Kirana & Artisa, 2020). These interests are very dynamic and adapt to the development of the existing collaboration process. Awareness of this needs to be emphasized and owned by every actor to strengthen the goals to be achieved. Activities that enhance the process of collaboration need to begin with a mapping of interests to find the intersections (Rohiani, 2021).

Communication can be a key to promoting development and applies to tourism-based village development (Flye et al., 2021). Communication activities need to be carried out regularly to strengthen the village development vision and strengthen the activities to be carried out. Another critical step is to attempt to institutionalize activities that communicate these with official forums with clear goals and directions (Saptana et al., 2014). As the leader who is

expected to create collaboration, the village government needs to strengthen with an understanding of the developments that will take place in collaborative governance.

Collaboration Platform

Figure 1 Platform governance logic
sumber: Ansell & Gash (2018:12)

In Figure 1, it can be seen that in matters of collaboration, the village government needs to consider the form of the container to be used. Consideration of the collaboration process will continue to feel the control of the rules and the strength of the role of each member. Nine platform forms can be described according to the type contained therein. The stronger the regulations that bind each actor, the more each actor must properly obey and carry out their functions on the platform. In addition, from a role perspective, it can be seen from a catalytic and aggregative role. Every actor who has a uniform role, then the part of each actor will be increasingly a catalyst and vice versa. On this platform, no type or model is the best, but suitability considers the needs and suitability of solving the issues or affairs needed.

In line with existing models, the role of the leader is a challenging task to determine the shape and design of the collaboration arena. Giving the role of leader to the government is the most sensible thing to encourage development that uses regional autonomy. Selection of an appropriate platform requires a long process and a good understanding from the government to provide a platform. Of course, the government has the resources and authority to create the arena. The government, as the regulator, needs to continue to participate in supervising the implementation process of each collaborative governance in every matter (Emerson, 2018). Thus, collaborative governance in each process can run well and be legally accounted for. Collaboration offers various advantages in the governance process that can benefit multiple parties.

Consideration of containers that can be used in collaboration in the development of tourist villages is the matching platform container model. Determining the use of the forum is done by considering the diversity of collaboration members from the village government, the private sector, village communities, mass media, and academics who can carry out their activities according to needs. On the other hand, using this platform also provides space for the village community to carry out more supporting activities according to the capabilities of the village community.

D. Conclusion

The conclusions that can be drawn according to the data and studies from this research process are as follows:

1. Leadership can be initiated by the village government and maintained through strengthening activities based on the ultimate goal of developing a tourist village. A long-term vision of the importance of developing a tourist village needs to be prepared with various detailed needs.
2. Actors who can be involved in collaborative tourism village development are various parties who have an interest and are regulated by the village government.
3. Goals and interests must be maintained by the parties involved in the collaboration process. It is essential to maintain continuity of collaboration with regular communication between actors with annual meetings that are included in the village deliberation agenda.
4. Platforms can be created to adjust interests and actors that could be stronger in principle and have a more aggregative role.

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